

You want to do Community Science (<https://communitysci.org/>), what now?

Five Questions to Get Started

1. **Goals:** What are you and your community's goals for this project?
 - a. What changes would you like to see in 10 or 15 years? What would you like to protect or preserve?
2. **Needs:** What are your community's immediate needs, and how can this project be designed to address them?
 - a. How can you meaningfully collaborate with a partner institution to meet these needs?
3. **Products:** What deliverables can be produced to support your community's goals and needs?
 - a. Useful and applicable products can go beyond a publication or peer-reviewed article, such as interactive maps, infographics, or a community awareness-raising initiative. See "Projects and Partnerships Brainstorming" for more examples.
4. **Engagement:** How do you intend to engage with your community about your project? How is this similar or different to how your community typically engages or communicates?
5. **Resources:** What funding or other resources are necessary, and who will provide them?

Project and Partnership Brainstorming

Identifying Partners

- Brainstorm a list of potential partners to contact in your area. Community science partners are not always strictly scientific institutions, but can also be local government offices, local schools and universities, activist groups or clubs, nonprofit organizations, etc.

Project Ideas

Community Science projects (<https://communitysci.org/projects/>) can take place in many forms and on varying scales. Once you have identified a main challenge, consider your project's desired outcomes:

- Some projects are turned into papers that are published on the Community Science Journal (<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/26929430>), a peer-reviewed, open-access publication dedicated to work that is performed by, with and for communities.
- Other projects produce reports, such as this GHG Inventory (<https://communitysci.org/durango-colorado/>) for a small city in Colorado.
- Some desired results target a long-term goal, such as this project (<https://communitysci.org/natchitoches-louisiana/>) which created hydraulic and hydrologic models in order to implement a flood management plan in the future.

Final Items to Consider

- Know your worth. Your community project should be an equal exchange. Scientific institutions benefit from helping communities just as much as you benefit from them helping you!

- Keep in mind attitudes surrounding STEM in your community. Reflect on your community's relationship with science--past, present, and future.
- Aim for scientific collaboration rather than exclusion.
 - o Consider potential barriers for your community. This includes things such as time of day, internet access for online meetings, job schedules, not feeling welcomed, etc.
- Know how your partner institution can reflect the community you serve. If applicable, address how they will treat cultural knowledge and foster inclusion.
 - o How do you and your community's goals align with your partner institution's mission?
- Address any boundaries with your partner institution in the beginning phases.
 - o Transparency in both parties is the key to trust. What does it mean for your institution to remain transparent?

Next Steps

Once you have outlined the goals, challenges, and desired outcomes for your project, it is time to begin planning. You can begin taking concrete steps by doing the following:

- Build strong relationships
 - o Set up meetings with involved parties. Build your project around respect and connections with others. Ensure that each player is ready to base the project on scientific evidence, not a political agenda.
- Communicate with your community
 - o Consider the people you will be communicating with and the best method of reaching them (i.e. a town hall, regular meetings, social media, etc.).
 - o Be sure to explain your project in plain, accessible language. Be sure your partner institution communicates without scientific jargon.
- Identify the key stakeholders in your project
 - o Acknowledge the needs of all parties involved with respect. Find mutual goals and be prepared to adjust your plans as new information is shared.
- Determine the scope and scalability of your project
 - o Addressing local problems doesn't mean you can't think broadly. Scientific knowledge can provide community members with information that makes them strong advocates for local, national, and global issues.
- Set up plans with your partner institution
 - o A good starting place is conducting a needs assessment to gather all needs and questions from your community. Be sure to set clear, measurable goals for your project team as well as expectations for communication and regular check-ins.

Further Reading:

Community Science is a powerful tool, so we recommended doing thorough research before jumping in. This abridged guide is based on information collected from the following suggested readings:

Meaningful Collaborations Workbook- https://communitysci.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/25/2024/04/CBO_Workbook_20190125-web.pdf

Community Science Guidance for Scientists - <https://thrivingearthexchange.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Community-Science-Guidance-for-Scientists.pdf>

Ethical science and collaboration - <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2022AV000762>

Ready to start a project?

Consider applying at <https://thrivingearthexchange.org/community-applications/>

Submit or access current resources at <https://communitysci.org/csehub/>